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Comparison of 3D and GIS approach for estimation rooftop solar potential in urban areas

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Abstract. Estimating rooftop solar power potential and PV power potential is in last two decades one of the most important topics in the field of decarbonisation and sustainable energy use. In terms of calculation tools, 3D softwares are usually more computationally and manually demanding compared to GIS tools, especially in the scale of urban blocks, districts or entire cities. On the other hand, lower demands of GIS tools are hand in hand with possibly lower accuracy. Therefore, it can be beneficial to calibrate the GIS model using real measured data or trusted results of 3D software and then use it for the calculation of larger urban areas. In this paper the GIS software was calibrated using long-term meteorological data and PVGIS data on horizontal plane. Next, it was compared with PVGIS and 3D model on a single tilted plane, with a fair agreement. Finally, the GIS and 3D software were compared using sums of total annual incident solar energy on five selected roof segments in the city centre of Prague. Despite several issues to be solved the difference in the total solar energy received by five selected roofs was at maximum $\pm 14\%$.

1. Introduction

The solar potential is a fundamental parameter in estimation the PV power potential. One of the most sufficient surfaces to be used for PV installation are building rooftops [1]. Together with floating PV on larger water bodies (reservoirs) and PV along roads and trails, these are by JRC referred as R3 installations [1]. These surfaces present a viable option for PV panels installation without occupying additional land. At the same time, also installations in agriculture dwellings (i.e. agrivoltaics) seem very promising [2].

In last two decades has been made a huge progress in the field of estimating rooftop solar energy potential in urban areas as well as progress in new calculation tools and software [3-5]. This was forced by increasing need of using renewable energy sources [6]. For estimation rooftop solar potential of large areas the most advantageous seems to be GIS tools, recently often combined with artificial intelligence and deep-learning approaches for generation 3D model of studied area [7]. Still the most accurate seem to be using a 3D software tools such as Rhino3D [8]. These can be however highly manually and computationally demanding. Therefore, a natural way to calculate rooftop solar potential of large urban areas is calibrating the GIS model based on real measured data or accurate outputs from 3D software on limited amount of buildings and then use the GIS software for larger urban bodies, such as building blocks, districts or entire cities.

This paper presents a process of calibrating GIS model based on local meteorological data and on results of 3D software. At first were compared ERA5-based data of annual total and diffuse insolation on horizontal plane (Hth [kWh/m²/a]) and (Hdh [kWh/m²/a]) with long-term average from local meteorological station and with data from PVGIS tool [9]. In the next step were compared calculated insolation values on sloped unshaded surface in 3D and GIS software and finally, the total annual incident solar energy on five real roofs within an urban block in the city centre of Prague, Czech Republic.

2. Methods

2.1 Software and input data

In this study were used two software tools. The 3D simulations were conducted in the Rhino3D 6.0[8] with Ladybug plugins. The base 3D model was downloaded from the website of Prague Institute for Planning and Development (IPR) [10]. For maximizing the accuracy of calculations the annual irradiance component has been used, translating the geometry and relevant information into a Radiance tool [11] for raytracing analysis using an enhanced two-phase method, which accurately models direct sun by tracing rays from each sensor to the solar position at each hour of the calculation. The input weather file contains hourly data of typical meteorological year TMYx epw file for the set of years 2007-2021. The solar radiation used in the TMYx file originated from the ERA5 [12] and reanalysed dataset provided by Oikolab.

For GIS calculations was used ArcGIS pro 3.4 [13] and solar radiation tool "Area Solar Radiation". The base digital elevation model (DEM) and polygons of building footprints were downloaded from the same institute as data for the 3D model, the IPR [10]. The DEM has a resolution (the cell size) of 1x1 m². The solar radiation tool in ArcGIS uses spatial solar model for the simulation of the sun orbit around the Earth. Therefore, no input meteorological data are needed for the irradiation calculations. There are only two parameters to be adjusted that represent the local atmospheric conditions, the atmospheric transmissivity (T) and the diffuse proportion (DP). Although the default values of the parameters provided in the software are sought to be sufficient for a good approximation of real annual insolation, it was shown in other studies that calibration of these parameters for local conditions is very beneficial [14,15].

2.2 Location and reference solar data

The location to be studied is the city centre of Prague (Czech Republic), 14.42°E, 50.08°N. As a reference solar data were used 16-year (hourly) data from local meteorological station on a horizontal plane. By simply averaging the data was established a reference irradiation year for purposes of this study. Figure 1 shows the reference year using monthly insolation values on horizontal plane, the total insolation (Hth) and diffuse part (Hdh). The right axis shows ratio of the diffusive and total insolation (Hdh/Hth).

Although for the calculation in Rhino were used different meteorological data (see Section 2.1), they are close to the reference year (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Long-term average of meteorological solar data (reference year) and meteorological data as the input in Rhino3D (based on ERA5) [12].

3 Calculations

3.1 Calculations on horizontal plane

As a base line for further complex scenarios the Rhino (3D model) and the GIS model was used to calculate insolation on an unshaded horizontal plane. The annual total (Hth) and diffuse (Hdh) insolation were compared. For more complex comparison also data from PVGIS tool [9] were added, see Table 1.

Except for the ArcGIS with default parameters, all sources are in good agreement with the reference meteorological year. In terms of (Hth), the maximum difference is ca. $\pm 4\%$ and in terms of diffuse horizontal insolation (Hdh) up to $\pm 17\%$. The ArcGIS with default parameters differs from the reference year by -20% (see Table 1). Therefore, the parameters were manually adjusted for getting values similar to the input data in Rhino, because these two software tools will be used for further calculations. Best fitting parameters were found to be $T = 0.44$ and $DP = 0.59$.

Table 1. Comparison of annual solar radiation data on horizontal plane.

Source	data information	Hth (kWh/m ²)	dif.	Hdh (kWh/m ²)	dif.	Hdh/Hth (-)
Prague meteostation (CHI) (reference year)	average (2004-2019)	1173	0%	585	0%	0.50
Rhino3D 6.0	TMYx ERA5	1224	4%	659	13%	0.54
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-ERA5 (2005-2023)	1138	-3%	487	-17%	0.43
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-SARAH3 (2005-2023)	1171	0%	569	-3%	0.49
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky; default T=0.5, DH=0.3)	942	-20%			
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky; default T=0.44, DH=0.59)	1220	4%	650	11%	0.53

3.2 Calculations on tilted plane

Effect of tilted plane was briefly studied on a single unshaded surface, similarly to the previous comparison on the horizontal plane. A slope of 38° and azimuth 165° clockwise from the north was selected. Only the results from Rhino, ArcGIS and PVGIS were compared, see Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of annual solar radiation data on tilted plane.

Source	data information	Hth (kWh/m ²)	dif.
Rhino3D 6.0	TMYx ERA5	1398	0%
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-ERA5 (2005-2023)	1411	1%
PVGIS ver.5.3	PVGIS-SARAH3 (2005-2023)	1365	-2%
ArcGIS Pro 3.1	AreaSolarRadiation tool (uniform overcast sky; default T=0.44, DH=0.59)	1325	-5%

3.3 Calculations on real roof segments

Five roof segments within an urban block in the city centre of Prague were selected for the final analysis. Roofs were selected to fulfil different aspects that can play a role in the total annual incident solar energy. Roof segments have different slope, orientation, and some are shaded or structured (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Orthophoto view on urban block in the city centre of Prague with highlighted roof segments to be analysed.

Figure 3. Comparison of orthophoto view (left), Rhino3D model view (middle) and ArcGIS Pro view (right) on a single roof segment.

One of the main problems can be towards the resolution of the GIS model, which is 1x1 m. Therefore, small structures in the plane of the roof are not respected in detail, but they affect the azimuth and slope of particular calculation cell. The more complex the roof is, the higher the potential error. In Figure 3 can be seen differences between the orthophoto view, the 3D software and in the GIS software view of the roof no.1.

In the 3D software is every segment of the roof defined in terms of its shape, area, azimuth and slope. In contrast, in GIS the roof is defined by the top-view polygon and raster of cells with an elevation information and the orientation and slope is defined by the elevation of neighbouring cells. Since four out of five selected roof segments are tilted, their top-view polygons do not represent their real area. If the slope is around 30°, the area of the roof is ca. 15 % larger than the polygon. At the same time, the result of used solar radiation tool in ArcGIS is the annual insolation ($\text{kWh/m}^2/\text{a}$) in the location of each calculation cell. Although the cells have top-view dimensions of 1x1 m^2 , these values do not correspond to the cell area, only to its location, orientation and slope, default for 1x1 m^2 size, which only by the chance is also the resolution of our cells. To obtain real incident solar energy on the sloped cell the insolation value has to be multiplied by the real sloped cell area. For this purpose, it was calculated slope and real area of each cell of the roof. This raster was then multiplied by the insolation raster to get real insolation in the whole top-view roof polygon.

The described operation had, however, another limitation. Due to the raster resolution, the slopes at the edges near eaves and on the border with other buildings were often calculated to be higher than 80°. These in reality are mostly vertical surfaces (walls). Problem is that calculated “real” area of these cells can be up to 10 m^2 (see Fig. 4) and at the same time the cell can have quite high insolation value calculated based on different GIS tool and. By multiplying the two values can be reached high insolation values in the cell, see Figure 4. Since these surfaces are not roofs, all slopes higher than 60° were set to maintain 60° slope. Although this can be studied in greater detail, the solution was assumed sufficient for this study.

Figure 4. Approach to avoid cells with solar energy values referring to walls: a) initial calculation or solar energy raster, b) raster of real cell areas including some side walls, c) raster of (a) and (b) multiplied containing error cells, d) adjusted area raster without area of walls, e) adjusted raster of solar energy on roofs (multiplication of (a) and (d)).

In Table 3 can be seen results of total incident solar energy on all roof segments calculated in Rhino and ArcGIS Pro software. Despite very different calculation approaches the resulting values are in good agreement. It can be seen that mean insolation on selected roof segments differs up to $\pm 8\%$, the roof area up to $\pm 11\%$ and the total annual incident solar energy up to $\pm 14\%$.

Table 3. Comparison of calculated annual solar energy and area of five roof segments in the city of Prague based on Rhino3D and ArcGIS approaches.

		insolation (kWh/m ² /a)	area (m ²)	total incident solar energy (MWh/a)
roof 1	Rhino3D	1156.8	152.0	175.8
	ArcGIS Pro	1150.1	142.6	164.0
	dif.	-0.6%	-6.2%	-6.7%
roof 2	Rhino3D	992.0	180.8	179.4
	ArcGIS Pro	915.6	200.3	183.4
	dif.	-7.7%	10.8%	2.3%
roof 3	Rhino3D	321.8	189.4	61.0
	ArcGIS Pro	325.1	177.5	57.7
	dif.	1.0%	-6.3%	-5.3%
roof 4	Rhino3D	847.8	82.1	69.6
	ArcGIS Pro	798.4	90.3	72.1
	dif.	-5.8%	9.9%	3.5%
roof 5	Rhino3D	830.0	186.1	154.5
	ArcGIS Pro	806.9	165.2	133.3
	dif.	-2.8%	-11.2%	-13.7%
total			790.5	640.3
			775.9	610.5
			-1.9%	-4.7%

4 Discussion

The parameters of ArcGIS solar radiation tool were at first manually adjusted to fit the total and diffuse insolation on horizontal plane with the meteorological data that were used in Rhino (see Figure 4). Table 3 shows that after this adjustment the annual incident solar energy on selected roof segments in the city centre of Prague corresponds well with reference values calculated in Rhino software. None of the five selected roofs with different shading, slopes and orientation differ more than $\pm 14\%$ from reference values. Moreover, the results contain some amount of error given by the differences in roof areas between the Rhino and ArcGIS software. At the same time the differences in solar radiation mostly correspond to differences in roof area, see Table 3. It can be therefore estimated that if the area in both models (3D and GIS) would be the same, differences in incident solar energy will be even lower.

In the context of all five selected roof segments together which can represent a building block made out of these roofs, the difference between models is only around -5% , which can be considered a good agreement. On the other hand, a set of five roofs is still not statistically sufficient to draw general conclusions about the accuracy of the GIS software. The preliminary results are, however, promising.

If the error of incident solar energy calculated in GIS software will be proved to be still within $\pm 14\%$ for any type of the urban area within the city, this calculation approach can be suggested to be used at least for usual purposes, such as estimating the power potential of a single roof in terms of PV installation (after practical analysis of real installation area, especially after subtracting the area covered by windows, etc.) and even for the estimation of solar power potential of the whole city.

Based on current results a further work can be proposed: 1) performing a comparison of the full building block containing ca. 30-40 buildings and for different types of urban areas (e.g. city centre with historical buildings, suburban area, industrial areas), 2) The calculation can be performed not only using the annual sums of incident solar energy, but also using monthly values with GIS parameters calibrated for each month, 3) the comparison of incident rooftop solar energy can be performed using not only the total values but also the direct and diffuse parts.

5 Conclusion

Step-by step comparison of 3D and GIS approach for the estimation of annual incident solar energy on selected roof segments showed that using the GIS software can be sufficiently accurate for usual purposes. However, this can be done only by proper calibration of the model parameters and careful postprocessing, especially towards calculating real (sloped) roof area. The comparison of five selected roof segments located in real urban area in the city centre of Prague showed maximum $\pm 14\%$ difference in total annual incident solar energy compared to a reference 3D software. This difference we see still sufficient for the use of GIS software at least for usual purposes, such as estimating a single roof power potential in terms of PV installation.

This study was limited only to solar potential of rooftops in general, without more practical insight, such that considerable area of roof surfaces is covered with windows, ventilation exhausts, etc. Therefore, for estimating realistic PV power potential of selected roofs an additional practical analysis would be needed.

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